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ATTITUDE OF INDIVIDUAL TAX PAYERS TOWARDS E-FILING OF INCOME TAX RETURNS

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ABSTRACT

Income tax is a key source of funds that any government uses to finance its activities and serve the public. It has been aptly said that taxes are the price we pay for civilization. The tax system of a country, thus, reflects the social, economic and political aims of the Government. The tax administration is revamped to treat taxpayers as customers. The Income Tax Department of the Ministry of Finance, Government of India, is committed to provide world – class services to taxpayers in the country, making tax compliance easy and convenient. One of the initiatives of the Income Tax Department was the introduction of Electronic filing (e-filing) of income tax returns (ITRs) to make the filing process easier for taxpayers as well as to reduce the time required for data entry on receipt of returns. Enabling the filing of ITRs over the Internet was the most viable answer to the department's needs. While the facility would be beneficial to the taxpayers, the department had to create an environment wherein the user would feel secure about filing his ITRs online. E - Filing helped furnishing ITRs through authorized intermediaries who were called "e-Return Intermediaries". Response time for processing the ITRs as well as claiming refund dropped significantly. Duplication of efforts was eliminated since data entered by intermediaries was already available in the system for any time use and reference. This paper has highlighted the awareness level of individual tax payers towards e-delivery services through computerization initiatives, the level of awareness among the tax payers towards e-governance initiatives of the government and the acceptance level towards various aspects of E-filing of Income tax returns.

Key words: E-filing, ITRs, TARC, E-Governance, awareness.

INTRODUCTION :

The online process did not require the taxpayers to be physically present for filing their ITRs. Thus, E - Filing is a system for submitting tax documents to the Income tax department through the internet or direct connection, usually without the need to submit any paper documents. The newly set up Tax Administration Reforms Commission (TARC) seeks to remove the daily barriers and obstacles faced by taxpayers as part of its attempt to identify the critical mass of administrative steps required to strengthen the tax system. The TARC also looks to protect "good taxpayers" and ensure that they are treated as valuable customers of the Tax Department. Efforts are taken to remove the "small irritants" so that small taxpayers "cheerfully" comply with the tax provisions. E-filing helped furnishing income tax returns through authorized intermediaries who were called e-return intermediaries. Response time for processing the income tax returns as well as claiming refund dropped significantly.

BENEFITS OF E-FILING OF INCOME TAX RETURNS

- Return can be prepared and filed by the tax payer through electronic mode
- Enables citizens to file "anytime & from anywhere".
- Saves time of the tax payer.
- Interface between ITD and the assessee reduced.
- Saves time of the ITD in dealing with the returns in physical forms.

- Saves issue up of record keeping & requirement of physical space.
- Easy availability of returns ensured.
- Accuracy of data ensured.
- Enables faster processing of returns.

There is also an advantage of acknowledgement from centralized processing centre (CPC), Bangalore about the receipt of ITR. Tools are available in e-file software to assist the assesses to claim deductions and credits, including the earned income tax credit, child and dependent care expenses Credit and business incentives etc. IRS has achieved a good e-filing participation rate, but in order to improve it more security techniques should be updated from time to time.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Geetha and Sekar (2012) have conducted a survey focusing on assessing awareness and satisfaction level of tax payers about e-filing of income tax returns in Coimbatore city. In their study they have found that majority of the individual tax payers are satisfied with the various aspects of e-filing and a significance relationship is found between residential status and the level of awareness regarding usage of e-forms and Awareness of e-filing procedure. They have concluded that new technologies are introduced to save the tax payers' saves golden time, energy and cost and also reduces tension.

Alabede et al (2011) have made a study on individuals whose incomes are taxable under the provisions of Personal Income Tax Act ,2004 in Nigeria. They measured the three dimensions of the taxpayer's attitude towards tax evasion and found that the respondents had fair ethnical behaviour towards tax system, felt bad about the involvement of others in tax evasions and tax fairness and unfavourable attitude towards tax evasion. The result from the study suggests that policy makers, particularly those in Nigeria should adopt strategies that would prop up taxpayers' attitudes against tax evasion, such strategies would likely have positive effect on taxpayers' compliance behaviour and consequently improve tax revenue collections.

Saini and Panjwani Vinita (2011) have studied the progress of e-taxation system in India by comparing its yearly progress on the basis of Income tax Returns. Their study proved that that there is equal progress in all assessment years and there is no significant change in the level progress. The positive flow of curve, was concentrated at the high end of the measuring scale which means values in their frequency distribution is moving towards higher end which indicates the increasing number of e-filer assesses. They concluded that e-taxation is like a dark horse in all its respect which has definitely shown some progressive outcome and it's surely going to make its full time place in the Indian Tax System.

Chidambaram and Vikkraman (2012) have identified that every nation's government survives and thrives on its tax collection. Henceforth slew of measures are being taken by our Indian government across the country to bring it more populace under the tax net for increased tax collection, without hurting the tax-payer's attitude.

Though many studies have been made on online filing in various countries , no study is made in India especially after launching the electronic filing of Income Tax Returns. No work has been carried out with reference e-filing adoption in the southern parts of Tamilnadu This study purports to fulfill this academic need.

OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the profile of individual tax payers and their tax compliance behaviour .
- To assess the tax payers awareness level towards e-delivery services through computerization initiatives.
- To analyze the level of awareness among the tax payers towards e-governance initiatives of the government.
- To understand the acceptance level towards various aspects of income tax system

METHODOLOGY

The study is limited to individuals who are tax payers in Virudhunagar District. The sample for the study is individual taxpayers who have used the e-filing system and hoping to re-use it again. The primary data were used in this study; data were collected from individual tax payers. As this is an exploratory study, a self administered structured questionnaire is used to gather the data. A total of 480 responses are used for the purpose of the analysis. . The statistical tools are used to test the significance level; the tools like Friedman test, correlation analysis are used by feeding the data in SPSS 17.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In India, the individual tax payers are still unorganized. Other than government and private employees, sole traders, agents, sole proprietors and many other income groups are unorganized and they haven't yet entered the tax system. Those who possess PAN and filing Income tax returns every year may be lesser than the total mass due to lack of awareness and fear of becoming a tax assessee. Hence the researcher tried to study the demographic profile of the tax assesseees in Virudhunagar district-an industrial district blessed with sufficient number of workers, businessmen and salaried class.

- **Profile of Individual Tax payers**

The profile of the sample tax payers is discussed by taking into consideration their personal data viz., Sex, Age, Occupation, Educational qualification, Occupation and Range of Taxable income in Lakhs,

Table 1: PROFILE OF INDIVIDUAL TAX PAYERS		
Gender	No. of ASSESSES	Percent
Male	269	56
Female	211	44
Total	480	100
AGE	No. of ASSESSES	Percent
Below 30	33	6.9
30-45	251	52.3
45-60	150	31.3
Above 60	46	9.6
Total	480	100.0
Educational Qualification	No. of ASSESSES	Percent
Upto HSc	136	28.3
UG	159	33.1
PG	119	24.8
Professional	66	13.8
Total	480	100.0
Occupation	No. of ASSESSES	Percentage
Academicians	47	9.8
Professionals	59	12.2
Business	189	39.4
Government Employee	140	29.2
Private Employee	45	9.4
Total	480	100.0
Range of Taxable income (in lakhs)	Frequency	Percentage
Below 5	232	48.3
5-10	161	33.5
Above 10	87	18.1
Total	480	100.0

Source: Primary data

From the above table, it is clear that 56 per cent of the tax payers are male and 44 per cent of the tax payers are female. A majority of 52.3 per cent of the tax payers are between 30-45 years of age and 31.3 per cent of tax payers are between 46-60 years of age. 33.1 percent of the tax payers have completed their UG course Graduates and a minimum of 13.8 per cent of the tax payers are professionally qualified . The above table also illustrates that among the individual tax payers, 39.4 per cent are doing business 29.2 per cent are Government employees; 48.3 per cent of the individual assessee's taxable income is below 5 lakhs per annum and 33.5 per cent of the individual assessee's taxable income ranges between 5-10 lakhs per annum

- **Filing of income tax returns**

Under Income Tax Act, every person being an assessee whose total income is assessable for the previous year exceeds the prescribed exemption limit (i.e. maximum amount which is not chargeable to tax) is required to file, on or before the due date, a return of his income voluntarily in the prescribed form and verified in the prescribed manner.

Table 2: FILING OF INCOME TAX RETURNS		
No. of years filing returns	Frequency	Percentage
Below 5	142	29.6
5-10	277	57.7
Above 10	61	12.7
Total	480	100.0
Regularity in filing returns	Frequency	Percentage
Very regular and file before due date	142	29.6
Regular and file on the due date of filing return	338	70.4
Total	480	100.0
Term of possessing PAN Card	Frequency	Percentage
Before 2005	76	15.8
2005-2010	124	25.8
2010-2015	280	58.3
Total	480	100.0
Taxable income (in lakhs)	Frequency	Percent
Below 5	232	48.3
5-10	161	33.5
Above 10	87	18.1
Total	480	100.0
Term of filing of returns	Frequency	Percent
Below 5	142	29.6
5-10	277	57.7
Above 10	61	12.7
Total	480	100.0

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 57.7 per cent of the individual assessee's are filing their returns for more than 5 years and only 12.7 per cent of the individual assessee's were filing their returns for more than 10 years. 70.4 per cent were filing their income tax returns on the due dates regularly and 29.6 per cent of the individual assessee's are filing their returns very regular to the income tax department before the due date

of return.

The above table 2 also reveals that 58.3 per cent of the individual assesseees had got their PAN card during the years 2010-2015. reveals the fact that the awareness and importance of getting PAN card rose during the year 2010-2015 is found high because during this period only the E-Governance initiative of E-Filing of Income Taxation was implemented. 48.3 per cent of the individual assesseees taxable income is below 5 lakhs per annum, 33.5 per cent of the individual assesseees taxable income is ranges between 5-10 lakhs per annum

57.7 per cent of the individual assesseees were filing their returns for the term of 5 to 10 years, 29.6 per cent of the individual assesseees were filing their returns for the period of less than 5 years and 12.7 percent of the individual assesseees were filing their returns for the duration of more than 10 years.

• **Reason for filing of income tax returns**

As per Taxation Rules, it is mandatory for an earning individual/entity to file a return irrespective of the fact that tax has been deducted at source by his/her employer or not, and whether he/she is eligible for a refund or not. Paying income tax is a moral and legal obligation of every proud citizen of the country. The taxation system is designed to make sure there are no unnecessary taxes that may become a financial burden on the tax payer .The reasons for filing income tax returns are presented in the following table.

Reasons	Yes		No		Total	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Treat it as moral obligation	436	90.83	44	9.17	480	100
In response to notice from IT Department	101	21.04	379	78.96	480	100
Compulsory because of TDS-TCS made by employer	107	22.29	373	77.71	480	100
To carry forward of business loss	202	42.08	278	57.92	480	100
To avail loan/OD facility	195	40.63	285	59.38	480	100
VISA purpose	47	9.79	433	90.21	480	100

Source: primary data

From the above table, it is ascertained that 90.83 per cent of the individual assesseees are filing their returns as they consider it as moral obligation whereas a minimum of 9.17 per cent only don't treat it as a moral obligation. 42.08 per cent of the individual assesseees are filing their income tax returns to carry forward their business loss, whereas for 57.92 per cent there is no carry forward of their business loss. 40.63 per cent of the individual assesseees are filing their returns to avail loan/OD facility from banks and only 22.29 percent of the assesseees are filing their returns compulsorily as their employer deduct tax at source. 21.04 per cent of the assesseees have filed the returns in response to notice from IT department whereas a majority of 78.96 percent of assesseees file their returns voluntarily adhering to due date of filing the returns. Only 9.79 per cent of the assesseees have filed their returns for VISA processing.

LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF INDIVIDUAL ASSESSEES TOWARDS WEB-ENABLED SERVICES OF INCOME TAX DEPARTMENT

With modern information technology as a key driver, the CBDT is implementing a comprehensive computerization programme in the Income Tax Department. The programme is aimed to establish a taxpayer friendly regime, increase the tax-base, improve supervision and generate more revenue for the Government. The individual tax payers' level of awareness towards web-enabled services by the CBDT is studied in two dimensions-

- i) awareness towards E-governance initiatives of the department and
- ii) awareness towards e-delivery services offered

• **Level of awareness on E-Governance initiatives**

Ho1: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards level of awareness on e-governance initiatives

The researcher applied Friedman test, to test the above said hypothesis

Variables	Mean Rank	Chi-square value	p value
E-filing of returns	4.29	232.328	<0.001
Tax Information Network (TIN)	5.12		
Dedicated call centre	5.16		
Centralized processing Centre (CPC)	5.37		
Centralized Processing Cell (CPC)	5.46		
Refund Banker Scheme	5.47		
Sevottam Scheme	5.58		
Tax net project	5.62		
Business Process Re-engineering (BPR)	6.28		
Consolidation of e-services etc.	6.65		

Source: primary data

Since p value is less than 0.05, null hypothesis is rejected at 5 percent level of significance with regard to level of awareness of individual assesses towards e.governance initiatives. Hence it is concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards level of awareness on e-governance initiatives .

The mean ranks of the above table illustrates that among the ten variables relating to level of awareness on e governance initiatives, E-filing of returns(4.29) is ranked first, followed by Tax Information Network -TIN (5.12) and Consolidation of e-services etc(6.65). is ranked as the last one.

• **Level of awareness on E-Delivery services**

Ho 2: There is no significance difference among mean ranks towards level of awareness of e-delivery services

The researcher has applied Friedman test, to test the above said hypothesis

Variables	Mean Rank	Chi-square value	p value
E-Payment of taxes	4.54	214.417	<0.001
E- Delivery of refunds	4.87		
E-filing of Income Tax Returns	5.07		
E-filing of TDS statements	5.08		
E-Matching of tax credits	5.29		
E-Processing of TDS statement	5.70		
E-tracking of refunds	5.94		
E-view of tax credits	6.07		
E-Processing of Income Tax Returns	6.18		
E-tracking of processing of the income tax returns	6.26		

Source: primary data

Since P value is less than 0.05, null hypothesis is rejected at 5 percent level of significance with regard to level of awareness of individual assesses’ towards E-Delivery services of Income Tax Department. Hence it is concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards level of awareness on e-Delivery services of Income Tax Department .

The mean ranks of the above table illustrates that among the ten variables relating to level of awareness on e delivery services of the Income Tax Department, E-Payment of taxes(4.54) is ranked first, followed by E-Delivery of refunds(4.87) and the level of awareness towards the service E-tracking of processing of the income tax returns is ranked as the last one(6.26).

CORRELATION ANALYSIS ON DIMENSIONS OF WEB ENABLED SERVICES OF INCOME TAX DEPARTMENT

Simple correlation analysis is used by the researcher to understand the relationship between the six dimensions under which the implementation of web enabled services of income tax department is carried out namely Tax system, Tax administration, Tax assessment, E-governance, Security system and Social system. The results of correlation analysis is shown in the following table 7

Table 7: Correlation analysis on dimensions of web enabled services

Dimensions	Tax System	Tax administration	Tax Assessment	E-Governance	Security System	Social System
Tax System	1	.454**	.558**	.497**	.494**	.433
Tax administration		1	.390**	.555**	.326**	.493
Tax Assessment			1	.578**	.315**	.393
E-Governance				1	.319**	.626
Security System					1	.394
Social System						1

Note: ** Denotes significant at 0.05 level

From the table it is found that there exists positive correlation between the variables. The relationship between tax system and tax administration (r=45.4%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax system and tax assessment (r=55.8%) is strong and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax system and e-governance (r=49.7%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax system and security system (r=49.4%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax system and social system (r=43.3%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level.

The relationship between tax administration and tax assessment (r=39%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax administration and e-governance (r=55.5%) is strong and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax administration and security system (r=32.6%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax administration and social system (r=49.3%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level.

The relationship between tax assessment and e-governance (r=57.8%) is strong and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax assessment and security system (r=31.5%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between tax assessment and social system (r=39.3%) is moderate and is significant.

The relationship between e-governance and security system (r=31.9%) is moderate and is significant at 5% level. The relationship between e-governance and social system (r=62.6%) is strong and is significant at 5% level.

The relationship between security system and social system (r=39.4%) is moderate and significant at 5% level.

The above results brings forth the fact that E-Governance acts a strategic tool for transforming Governance and improving the quality of e tax services provided by the government to its people and the IT Department is free from corruption and bring in more transparency through e-filing.

CONCLUSION

This paper has highlighted the awareness level of individual tax payers towards e-delivery services through computerization initiatives, the level of awareness among the tax payers towards e-governance initiatives of the government and the acceptance level towards various aspects of E-filing of Income tax returns. Today security measures like SSL (Secure Socket layer) & 128 Bit encryption guard the safety of data and information. Digital Signature being treated equal to physical signatures, guaranteed authenticity of the electronic data, ensuring that no party repudiated the transaction, while protecting the data against any fraudulent changes. Thus the ease of use and users' feeling of control of the e-filing tax system would give them confidence about the new technology system. Finally, a user's perception about genuineness of the tax web, authenticity, trustworthiness and easiness of the process of filing tax returns can also be enhanced if user feels very knowledgeable about what he/she is doing when they are filing their tax returns electronically. Thus, the users' awareness and experience also help enhance their retention dramatically. So more efforts must be made in this direction by Indian Income Tax Department only then they can achieve their mission "Technology in the service of Tax Payers". The concept of e-filing is still evolving and is undergoing changes at a rapid pace. In the near future when the full system will be in place it is expected that it will bring a new face of the Finance Ministry as an organized and well administered entity.

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